

RESONANCE REACTION PART II.

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The formation of fumaric acid from maleic acid by resonance reaction has been completely established and the methyl ester characterised. The best yield of fumaric acid (50%) is obtained when maleic acid and MnO_2 exist in the proportion of 4 : 1. The conversion of citraconic acid to mesaconic acid by resonance reaction has been confirmed.

Neogi, Neogi and Chatterjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 279) first showed that maleic acid was partly converted into fumaric acid when sulphur dioxide was passed through a solution of maleic acid in which manganese dioxide was suspended and that neither sulphur dioxide nor manganese dioxide alone as well as the products of the reaction could bring about the conversion. This was repeated by Neogi and Mitra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 969) who confirmed the result and named such a reaction 'resonance reaction.' Owing to the importance of the result, the reaction was studied (i) to confirm further the formation of fumaric acid by preparing its methyl ester, (ii) to ascertain the conditions under which the best yield of fumaric acid is obtained varying the proportions of manganese dioxide and maleic acid. The formation of fumaric acid has now been completely established and its methyl ester characterised. It has been shown here that the best yield of fumaric acid (50%) is obtained when the proportions of maleic acid and manganese dioxide are about 4 : 1.

Neogi and Mitra (*loc. cit.*) also studied the conversion of citraconic acid to mesaconic acid. This experiment has also been repeated and the result confirmed. The best yield of 20% crude and 10% pure mesaconic acid was obtained when the proportion of citraconic acid to manganese dioxide was also about 4 : 1. The yield of mesaconic acid from citraconic acid is, as already mentioned in the earlier paper, much less than that of fumaric from maleic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Conversion of Maleic to Fumaric Acid.—To maleic acid (4 g.) dissolved in water (10 c.c.), a rapid current of sulphur dioxide was passed for about 5 minutes. As soon as manganese dioxide disappeared a white precipitate rapidly separated. This was filtered and crystallised from alcohol. About 1 g. of this substance was esterified with methyl alcohol (2 g.) and sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) by heating on a steam-bath for about 4 hours. The methyl ester after purification had m.p. 100° , undepressed by an authentic specimen.

TABLE I.

Maleic acid.	MnO ₂ .	Duration of passage of SO ₂ .	Yield of fumaric acid.
4.0 g.	0.1 g.	5 min.	Nil
4	1.0	"	50%
4	2.5	Till MnO ₂ disappeared.	35%
4	4.0	Do	Very small.
2	4.0	Do	Do

Conversion of Citraconic Acid to Mesaconic Acid.—To a suspension of manganese dioxide (0.5 g.) in a solution of citraconic acid (2 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was passed sulphur dioxide till a clear solution resulted (3 or 4 minutes). The filtered solution was evaporated on the steam-bath and the residue extracted with ether, the ethereal layer being washed with equal volume of water. The removal of ether furnished pure mesaconic acid (*cf.* Franz, *Monatsh*, 1894, 15, 209), m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen 202°. Mesaconic acid can be alternatively isolated by precipitation from the solution with ferric chloride as a brown compound whence after liberation with hydrochloric acid, it can be extracted out with ether. The acid isolated from the ether layer requires two crystallisations.

TABLE II.

Citraconic acid.	MnO ₂ .	Duration of passage of SO ₂ .	Yield.
2.0 g.	0.1 g.	Till solution	Nil
2	0.5	"	10%
2	1.0	"	8.5 (15% crude)
2.5	2.0	"	5%
2.0	5.0	"	Very small.

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